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Historical Sciences

THE MAIN STAGES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF DOMESTIC TOURISM IN RUSSIA IN 2000-2020

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Abstract

The article shows that the main goal of domestic tourism is the most complete, rational and efficient use of available resources that make up the overall potential of the territory that has attractiveness for tourists. Accordingly, the most important tasks here include the following: the formation of rational spatial design programs with the mandatory development of all necessary infrastructure; the creation and maintenance of conditions for economic growth; attracting investment; creating conditions for improving the competitiveness of business entities in the tourism industry, stimulating the attraction of highly qualified personnel to the industry.

Keywords: tourism, potential, history, country, leader.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism, among the existing elements of the infrastructure complex of the territory, stands out especially, because it is not a separate industry, but a whole complex of industries: hotel business, restaurant business, sightseeing, etc. For the implementation of tourist projects, in addition to the tourism business itself, it is also necessary to involve transport, cultural and entertainment and other spheres. Effective provision of tourist routes and provision of high-quality tourist services requires the development, in fact, of all elements of the infrastructure complex of the region, the country: road, engineering, transport and logistics, industry. In turn, the development of domestic and inbound tourism (i.e., an increase in the number of tourists, which is possible if there are attractive tourist facilities, a positive image of the region, security guarantees, a sufficiently high level of infrastructure development) necessarily entails further improvement of infrastructure complexes. The development of transport infrastructure is of particular importance for those regions for which the tourism sector becomes the main strategic choice.

Tourism, assuming the creation of all the necessary conditions for staying at a sufficiently high level, will entail the development of the main groups of infrastructure services: social, environmental, technological, organizational, informational both at the regional level and, ultimately, at the country level.

In turn, the development of infrastructure as a "link" for various enterprises and organizations and as a basis for improving the life of the population stimulates the processes of socio-economic integration of the country's regions.

II. METHODOLOGY

The article uses such scientific approaches to conducting research as system analysis, modeling, methods of comparison and grouping, methods of economic and statistical analysis. The results of scientific research and practical activities of the author were used, statistical materials were analyzed that demonstrate the conditions for the formation and development of tourism projects in the Central Federal District of the Russian Federation, as well as legal documents regulating the tourism industry and publicly available results of scientific research of domestic and foreign scientists.

III. RESULTS

Domestic tourism - tourism within the territory of the Russian Federation of persons permanently residing in the Russian Federation. Tourism is a powerful global industry in which huge masses of workers and fixed assets are involved; this is a category that is strongly influenced by economics and politics. And they carry out and organize the service of tourists by enterprises of the tourism industry - travel agencies in cooperation with hotel enterprises and catering enterprises. The importance of tourism as a stimulator for the development of other sectors of the economy, such as construction, trade, production of consumer goods, communications, etc. is constantly growing. In the tourism industry, the dynamics of growth in the volume of services provided leads to an increase in the number of jobs not much faster than in other industries. The time interval between the growth in demand for tourism services and the emergence of new jobs in the tourism business is minimal. This business attracts entrepreneurs for many reasons: small start-up investments, growing demand for tourist services, high profitability. Despite the ongoing tourist boom in Russia, the impact of tourism on the country's economy is still insignificant, since the state, in turn, is characterized by a lack of real investment in this area of the economy, a low level of partial service, an insufficient number of hotel beds, and a shortage of qualified personnel. Within a country, tourism contributes to the stability of the national economy. Tourism has a positive impact on maintaining world peace. Increasing the interest of one people in the culture of another leads to mutual understanding.

The presence of various tourist and recreational assets of the country allows the development of almost all types of tourism. On the territory of the Russian Federation, both traditional tourist centers have developed with a specialization in a certain type of tourism (Moscow, St. Petersburg), as well as recognized interregional products and routes (Golden Ring, cruises on the Volga River). Beach tourism is one of the most popular types of recreation among Russians. According to expert estimates, 38 percent of Russian tourists prefer to relax on the Black Sea and Azov coasts (Southern Federal District), as well as on the Baltic coast (North-Western Federal District) and the beaches of the Sea of Japan (Far Eastern Federal District). Promising regions in terms of the development of this type of tourism are the regions of the Southern Federal District. There are more than 2,000 km of warm sea coasts in Russia, but only 1/3 of them are landscaped and suitable for a beach holiday. In 2020, about 20.5 million tourists rested at Russian beach resorts. With the appropriate development of this type of tourism, regions of the Russian Federation that are promising from this point of view will be able to receive an additional 25 million tourists a year for beach holidays. The historical and cultural heritage of Russia is the most important competitive advantage of the country's tourism industry. Travels for cultural and educational purposes account for about 20 percent of the domestic tourist flow. The Central and Northwestern Federal Districts are the centers of cultural and educational tourism in the country. In 2020, the number of tourists who traveled for cultural and educational purposes amounted to about 10 million people.

There are great potential opportunities for the development of this direction in certain regions of the Southern, Volga, Siberian and Far Eastern federal districts. However, the unsatisfactory state of the road transport and other tourist infrastructure of most of the regions of these federal districts that are promising from the point of view of cultural and educational tourism is a deterrent to the formation of a modern competitive tourist product. The development of this type of tourism will attract an additional 8 million Russian and foreign tourists annually. Of particular interest to Russia is the development of business tourism. Currently, about 70 percent of the total volume of trips for business purposes falls on the Central and Northwestern Federal Districts. At the same time, the business activity of other federal districts and the number of their contacts with foreign countries are constantly growing. General economic development, the construction of new and modernization of existing enterprises in various sectors of the economy, the intensive entry of foreign companies into the Russian market will determine the further growth of business tourism in most metropolitan cities, which will require the construction of modern business and congress centers, and an increase in exhibition space. The potential annual additional demand for this type of tourism is more than 10 million people. In addition, Russia has great potential for the development of active tourism (skiing, hiking, water, mountain, cycling, sailing, horseback riding). Since 2000, the process of becoming a network trade in tourist services has been actively developing. Network trade in travel services is represented by associations of legally independent operator companies and travel agencies operating under a single brand. There are currently about 10 network operators operating in the domestic market, among them are Hot Voyage Store, Turinfo Global Travel, Metropol-Express, Greenex, Kuda.ru, and Wind Rose.

Network associations are created on the basis of a franchise agreement. When concluding an agreement, the management company (franchisor) transfers its trade secrets to the travel agency (franchisee), trains the franchisee's employees, grants it the right to enter the market under its own brand, provides management and business support, includes it in its information databases, telephone directories assists in advertising. By granting the franchisee the right to use his trademark, the franchisor requires him to comply with certain rules regarding the current operations of the business. Receiving such serious support from the franchisor, the franchisee undertakes to deduct on a regular basis a certain percentage of the proceeds from franchising operations. At the same time, the franchisee does not lose its legal independence and has the right to conduct its own business. Franchisees are required to report on the sale of the franchised product to determine the amount of royalties to the franchisor.

Russia Outbound Tourism Spending by Leading Destination 2021/2022

The main idea of joining the network is the ability to connect to proprietary technologies of the management company. All parties to the franchise agreement must follow certain standards in financial, technological and administrative work.

Most franchise companies operate in Moscow. The exception, perhaps, is the Greenex network, which began with an agency in Yekaterinburg. In 1999 she opened her office in Moscow. Currently, Greenex unites 13 agencies: in addition to 7 Moscow agencies, there are agencies in Chelyabinsk, Perm, St. Petersburg and Yekaterinburg. In 2001, Greenex launched a new ACS-Greenex program designed specifically for the network's functional diagram. The company considers the technological interaction of supplier operators and agents, the organization of a control system and advertising work to be the most important. Another direction of large investments is the opening of new points of sale. The cost of preparing and equipping one retail outlet is about 80 thousand dollars. Greenex offices are equipped according to a single standard, strictly following the corporate style. The payback period for a new office is 1.5-2 years. The Greenex management is also satisfied with its results, the main network performance indicators in 2018 increased by 1.5-2 times. The permanent client base of the network is about 10 thousand people, the rate of repeated requests is 70%.

In the Russian tourist market, financial structures are actively behaving, which are created by travel companies on their own investment projects. In 2000, the financial group "Tant'ema" created a network of travel agencies in Russia, using modern Western technologies. The principles of the network were developed with the involvement of American and European consultants. The trademark holder is a new company, Turalliance. The network companies are provided with a unified information system, corporate trainings, and their own marketing service engaged in market research and reliability of tour operators.

The new network association is included in the Six Sevens pool, which gives it a number of advantages. Six Sevens is a large trading pool. It includes such large companies as M.Video, Seventh Continent, Sportmaster, Arbat Prestige, etc. These names are well known to Russian consumers and have a reliable reputation. Being an equal partner of these firms, "Turalliance" participates in the joint advertising of the pool on radio, television, and in the press. Pool membership automatically raises brand prestige.

In 2020, tourist receipts plummeted due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Of the \$17.24 billion billion (2019), only \$4.96 billion billion remained. This is a 71 percent decrease in Russia.

The network is successfully developing thanks to the support of a strong financial investor. Currently, the network includes 17 own travel agencies and many franchise agencies, which are managed according to the same standards set out in the "Corporate Book". The requirement for compliance with standards, in particular, includes the uniformity of offices, the unique interior design of the office, and the mandatory branded clothing for managers. The strength of Turalliance is the high technological effectiveness of operations, the active use of electronic sales through the Kuda.ru website on the Internet, as well as participation in the Six Sevens pool, from which the end consumer benefits. On club cards, clients of the travel agency are provided with discounts on services and goods from other members of the pool.

The tourism business is one of the fastest growing sectors of the modern world economy. International tourism is one of the top three export industries, second only to the oil industry and the automotive industry. World tourism was especially widely developed in the 2nd half of the 20th century, due to a number of factors, tourism began to develop at a rapid pace, and this process tends to grow.

Factors contributing to the development of international tourism in the 2nd half of the 20th century:

1. Economic growth and social progress have led to an increase in business and educational travel.
2. The improvement of all types of transport has reduced the cost of travel.
3. The number of hired workers and employees in developed countries has increased, there has been an increase in their material and cultural level.
4. With the growth of the intensification of labor, workers receive longer holidays.
5. The development of interstate ties and cultural exchanges between countries has led to the expansion of interpersonal ties within the regions. The development of tourism is associated with the development of globalization - tourism is both its product and a factor in its further development. The growing interest of tourists in another culture, the availability of information contribute to an increase in the opportunities for communication between peoples, which allows people to better understand each other. Positive structural shifts in the domestic tourism industry in Russia are still being formed due to the post-crisis decline in the effective demand of the population and are not sustainable. With the growth of the welfare of the population, this trend may change again in favor of outbound tourism. To consolidate the positive trend in the structure of entry - exit, the only "substitute" factor is the creation of an attractive infrastructure for domestic and inbound tourism and a system of social tourism.

Domestic tourism expenditure in Russia from 2019 to 2021 (in billion U.S. dollars)

IV. CONCLUSION

The study showed that in recent years in Russia the tourism sector as a whole has been developing steadily and dynamically. There is an annual growth in the domestic tourist flow, the volume of investment proposals has sharply increased, while the main proposals are aimed at developing the hotel business in the regions of Russia. Of particular note are the successes of recent years in the development of the resort and tourist complex of the Krasnodar Territory, some regions of the Urals, Siberia, objects of the Golden Ring. The tourism infrastructure is also developing rapidly. The most dynamic growth is predicted for the tourist transport service industry, in particular for air transport.

The necessary conditions for the successful development of domestic tourism in Russia, as well as inbound tourism, are the formation of a high-quality tourist product, the availability of a competent marketing strategy for promoting the domestic tourist product on the Russian market, proven methods and mechanisms for implementing advertising and information policy, the creation of a system of professional training of personnel, attracting investments in the development of tourism infrastructure.

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ОСНОВНЫЕ ЭТАПЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ВНУТРЕННЕГО ТУРИЗМА В РОССИИ В 2000-2020 ГОДЫ

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Аннотация

В статье показано, что основной целью внутреннего туризма является наиболее полное, рациональное и эффективное использование имеющихся ресурсов, составляющих общий потенциал территории, обладающей привлекательностью для туристов. Соответственно, к наиболее важным задачам здесь относятся следующие: формирование программ рационального пространственного проектирования с обязательным развитием всей необходимой инфраструктуры; создание и поддержание условий для экономического роста; привлечение инвестиций; создание условий для повышения конкурентоспособности хозяйствующих субъектов в сфере туризма, стимулирование привлечения высококвалифицированных кадров в отрасль.

Ключевые слова: туризм, потенциал, история, страна, лидер.

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